

Ultrathin water layers on viruses

A.M. Bittner^{1*}, M.A. Iriarte-Alonso¹, J.H. Melillo², S. Cerveny², S. Chiantia³

¹CIC nanoGUNE (BRTA)/Ikerbasque, San Sebastián/Bilbao, Spain; ²Donostia. Intl. Phys. Center and Centro Fís. Mat., San Sebastián, Spain; ³Potsdam University, Germany

* a.bittner@nanogune.eu

Abstract:

For many viruses, transmission requires "survival" in dry conditions, specifically for the airborne route [1,2,3]. Simple plant viruses survive complete dehydration and exhibit an ultrathin water layer in ambient conditions [3,4]. For the complex enveloped viruses, the lipid bilayers must persist. How is this possible?

We first modelled the influenza A virus surface by hemagglutinin trimer "spikes" in supported lipid bilayers and investigated it by AFM and fluorescence correlation spectroscopy. We found that - in dry conditions - the spikes effectively block nano- and microscale restructuring, and slow lipid diffusion [1].

We proceeded by modelling the (glycosylated) spikes themselves by mannosylated gold particles, adsorbed on hydrophobic and on hydrophilic silane layers. AFM with hydrophobic and hydrophilic tips proves that glycosylation allows to retain ultrathin water layers (ca. 1 nm) even at low air humidity.

Lipid bilayers withstand drying in presence of the viral HA "spikes" (AFM)

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